

Generating Awareness on Disaster Management through the Science Festival

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ABSTRACT

Science festivals are the innovative method to introduce the scientific information for the children of various age groups. Every year Vigyan Prasar organize one national level live science festival in summer holidays through its EduSAT network and six virtual science festivals at various remote locations of the country. Through the science festival with the help of do yourself programme children can learn basic information about the science and technology. With the help of these science festivals Vigyan prasar caters more than five thousand children every year, they belongs to the urban area of various part of the country. Approximate 2000 children were participated in the science festival programme from the rural area of the country through virtual Science Festivals and 3000 children were participated in the live programme through EduSAT Network of Vigyan Prasar. To generate awareness for disaster management Vigyan Prasar developed an activity booklet on disaster management, Earthquake kit and movies on causes of disaster (Kedarnath). During the programme resource person (Subject experts) discuss the activity provide the time of to the activities and discuss the science behind it and during the session movie on Kedarnath also screened. After the programme children discuss and ask their queries with the resource person and also these children give the training to other groups. And motivate to others to participate in the programme and share their scientific talent.

Keywords: Activity booklet, Kit, Live, Science festival, Virtual

INTRODUCTION

Science communication generally refers to public communication presenting science related topics to non-experts. This often involves professional scientists but has also evolved into a professional field in its own right. It includes science exhibitions, journalism, policy or media production. To communicate science among the children it is necessary to make the topic interesting as well as involve the children in the programme where hands-on activity plays an important role. Vigyan Prasar is taking initiatives to develop different modes to take science to the people where learning science is a fun. Science Festival is one of such endeavours taken up by Vigyan Prasar. Vigyan prasar is organizing Science Festival for the children of the age group 10-15 year since 2007. When the initiative was first taken up, VP started with Science Documentary Movie Show followed by interactive session with the audience and subsequent discussion to remove the confusion and answering to the questions. In the next phase we incorporated Do-It Yourself (DIY) Activity based Science Festival where "Resource Material" in the form of low-cost kits was provided; but this was without any 'Reference Book'. Now Vigyan Prasar is providing "Resource Materials" (in Kit form) along with Resource Book to the children. These festivals turned out to be more interactive and useful for the children. They can rework on the activities.

Related work: For the programme two resource books are developed on disaster management for the children of age group 10-15 years jointly by Vigyan Prasar and National

Institute of Disaster management. Which are available in print as well as National Institute of Disaster management's website. (<http://nidm.gov.in/books.asp>) <http://nidm.gov.in/PDF/pubs/ACTIVITY%20BOOK%20DM.pdf>, <http://nidm.gov.in/PDF/pubs/Science%20Festival.pdf>, [2] and an activity kit on Earthquake in English and Hindi is available on www.vigyanprasar.gov.in [1].

Scope of research: with the help of science festival we can reach maximum numbers of the children and with do yourself activity booklet children learn in detail about the disaster and its management. First aid session helps to children to provide first aid on all circumstances.

Method: Vigyan Prasar provides all resource material and resource books to the children before commencement of the programme. First field test of the programme was done through EduSAT Satellite Interactive Terminal network where we conducted programmes from our Teaching End Terminal to various SIT Classrooms located at different parts of India. From Vigyan Prasar Studio, resource person starts the activity and scientific concepts of the activity. Children sitting at the various location of the country follow the resource person and do their experiments. All the queries coming through the network (Two way communication through EduSAT satellite – a Satellite built by ISRO exclusively for Education) for the rural area science festival resource person distribute the material to children and help them to do all the activities describe in the resource book [3].

CONCLUSION

every year approximate 5000 children are benefited with science festival from various part of the country. After that these children were help to the resource person during the

conducting of the science festival programme and help to the other children to understand the topics. For the EduSAT Network Vigyan Prasar organize two day programme on disaster management

Year	Children Participated in Disaster management and First Aid Programme programme Through EduSAT Network	Virtual Programme
2012	3000	2000
2013	2000	2000
2014	500 Participated till June 2014. And 1500 more children will be participated up to March 2015 approximate 3000 children will be participated in various programme	2000 more children will be participated up to March 2015 approximate 3000 children will be participated in various programme of which Programme will be organize at (Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Karnatka, Delhi, Utrakhand, etc.)

Live Session on disaster Management. Dir. NIDM is addressing to the children from Vigyan Prsar EdUSAT Studio.

Screening of movie at Uttar Pradesh

Science Festival children are working on activity booklet at Vigyan prasar EduSAT studio

Screening of movie at Uttar Pradesh

Children are working on Disaster Management activity booklet at Hyderabad.

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